

Living the Dream

by

Tom Heston

Living the Dream

Tom Heston

C **F** **Gm**
Moderato ♩=105

I'm search - ing for the mean - ing of where it's go - ing

Dm7 **C** **F**

I don't know the un-known search-ing for the feel - ing that sus - tains me

Gm7 **Dm7** **C**

lov-ing kind - ness let it flow in our life it grows so I Push back the dark-ness

Dm9 **Gm7** **F** **C**

Fill up with kind-ness push back the mean-ness fill up with lov - ing I'm dreaming

F **Gm** **Dm7**

of the bet-ter things that bring us all to - ge - ther we share it lasts for-

Living the Dream

C F Gm

ev - er Just see - ing and be - liev - ing the na - ture - that's con - nect - ing it

Dm7 C

brings out all the best thngs so I'm push-in' it back I'm push-in' it back I'm push-ing

Dm9 F maj7(9)

push-in' it back I'm push-in' it back I'm push - ing push-in' it back I'm

G9sus C

Allegro ♩=145

push-in' it back I'm push-ing push-in' it back the dark - ness yes I am a - live

Dm9 F maj7(9)

I am a - live liv - in' I am a - live I am a - live giv - in' I am a - live

G9sus C

I am a - live liv - in' I am a - live I'm - liv - in' the dream

Living the Dream

Dm7 G9sus C
a tempo ♩=105

and when it's time to go you will know I won't just walk a - way

G7sus Dm7 G7sus C

and when it's time to go you will know my lov - in' al-ways stays

G7sus C Bb F

I'm find - ing that feel - ing that brings us all to -

Gm7 C Bb

geth - er so beau - ti - ful so push a - way the dark - ness and fill it up with kind - ness I'm

F Gm7 C

dream - ing dream - ing of the bet - ter - life so fill it - up with kind - ness

Bb6 F Gm7

fill - it up with won - der it's so beau - ti - ful the lov - ing that - fills up our lives

Allegro ♩=145

Allegretto ♩=110

mp will sur -

vive I'm liv - in' I will get by by giv - in' I will sur - vive I'm giv - in'

mf I'm dream - ing of kind - ness

all of my love *ff* will sur - vive I'm liv - in' I will get

of laugh - ter com - pass - ion and

by by giv - in' I will sur - vive I'm giv - in' all of my love

when - I leave here my love - will

A will sur - vive I'm liv - in' I will get by by giv - in' I will sur -

be ev - er last - ing. I'm liv-ing the dream

vive I'm giv - in' all of my love

The first system of the score consists of a vocal line and a piano accompaniment. The vocal line is written in a single treble clef staff with a key signature of one flat (Bb) and a 4/4 time signature. The lyrics are: "be ev - er last - ing. I'm liv-ing the dream". The piano accompaniment is written in two staves (treble and bass clefs). The right hand features a series of chords, with the first two measures containing a whole note chord and the following two measures containing a half note chord. The left hand plays a simple bass line with quarter notes.

Allegro 60

The second system of the score is a piano accompaniment for the second system of the first system. It is written in two staves (treble and bass clefs) with a key signature of one flat (Bb) and a 4/4 time signature. The tempo marking "Allegro 60" is placed above the right-hand staff. The right hand features a series of chords, with the first two measures containing a whole note chord and the following two measures containing a half note chord. The left hand plays a simple bass line with quarter notes.

The third system of the score is a piano accompaniment for the third system of the first system. It is written in two staves (treble and bass clefs) with a key signature of one flat (Bb) and a 4/4 time signature. The right hand features a series of chords, with the first two measures containing a whole note chord and the following two measures containing a half note chord. The left hand plays a simple bass line with quarter notes.

Beyond Living the Dream. The genesis for this song came about during a personal health challenge. I could barely function, and most of my thoughts throughout the day concentrated on simply breathing. Sleep was almost impossible for several weeks, but I was still able to play the piano. During these moments of playing the piano, the music reaffirmed to me that our gift of life goes beyond the the pain, suffering, and tragedy that exists in our world. Even in the most dire circumstances, life still has great meaning. Ultimately, a strong love pushes back against the suffering and overcomes it. Pushing back can be hard, and can be life's greatest challenge. But we can and must do so with great vigor. We can fill the void with our highest value and aspiration: love.

Where do songs, ideas, and art all come from? Many people say their ideas simple come from out of thin air, or that a sudden inspiration comes from the universe. For me, some songs simply pop into my head, or I wake up singing a song that seemingly comes from a restful sleep or a beautiful morning (like *Country Joy*). Other songs, like *Living the Dream*, seem to come from a more organic source.

While playing the piano, alone in the dark at night, finding a brief respite from my illness, *Living the Dream* gradually came into existence. It is significant to mention the specific piano from which this music arose. It is a Weber 6' Grand Piano, made sometime around 1905. The piano was purchased at that time by the Mollison family, and my grandfather in-law Van Mollison learned to play on the piano. It has stayed in the family ever since, most recently with my mother-in-law Gail who played it often until she passed in 2017. Then just shortly after my diagnosis and near the time of my darkest hour healthwise, the piano arrived at our home. To me, it became a miraculous gift from God, facilitated by several generations of family. It helped me experience a spiritual rejuvenation, a powerful energy that affected my soul just like a shot of epinephrine can jump start a fibrillating heart.

This wonderful piano immediately found a comfortable home in our living room. It played beautifully from the start. The richness of the music was clearly greater than my limited piano playing talents. That "something out of the air" came through the piano, through its history, through its family heritage. The love the piano shared with previous family members seemed to be soaked up and richly stored in its wood, its hammers, its strings, and its keyboard. From this came a song that is greatly life affirming, a hopeful song that shows us that love is not limited by time. Love is unlimited, love is infinite. Love transcends our earthly existence, and can be passed along from generation to generation. Our bodies eventually wear out, but our love never dies. Even the smallest ripple of love has a profound and eternal significance.

Great joy comes from living the dream, from actively pushing back the darkness and filling it with light. What great delight and excitement this brings! It's truly the Good Life.

- TFH 7/22/2019